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ABSTRACT

Introduction: The educational needs of people with gestational hypertension during pregnancy are increasing day by day. This is because effective health management requires the transformation of knowledge about gestational hypertension management into behavioral changes. It is becoming increasingly common for individuals to seek online resources to access quality and readily available information on health management. YouTube, a widely accessible and free platform, may be particularly valuable for people with limited health literacy or barriers to receiving high-quality medical care. However, the quality and accuracy of YouTube videos varies considerably, and little is known about content relevant to gestational hypertension.

Objective: This study aimed to systematically assess the quality, content and reliability of YouTube videos addressing gestational hypertension.

Methods: A comprehensive YouTube search was conducted in February 2025 using the following keywords: 'gestational hypertension', 'pregnancy and hypertension', 'gestational hypertension treatment' and 'gestational hypertension management'. Search results were sorted by relevance to simulate a typical user experience. The first 60 videos (n=240) from each keyword were screened (Birch, 2022). Exclusion criteria included videos not related to gestational hypertension, those in languages other than English, duplicate videos, and videos without sufficient audio and video quality for analyses. Each unique video was assessed for accuracy and comprehensiveness using the gestational hypertension content score, while the DISCERN tool and Global Quality Score scale were used to measure reliability and quality (Yılmaz, 2024). We classified the videos in the study into three quality subgroups according to the scores they received on all three scales. Descriptive analyses were performed to compare video characteristics between different sources and quality ratings.

Results: The distribution of the 147 unique videos included between the groups is as follows: Low quality group included 49 videos with a total score between 3 and 6, medium quality group included 49 videos with a total score between 7 and 10, and high quality group included 49 videos with a total score between 11 and 15. The median number of views of the videos included in our study was 34002 (interquartile range (IQR): 4598 - 118680) and the median video duration was 262 (IQR: 188 - 738) seconds. The median popularity score was 32.5 (IQR: 5.4 - 121) and the median power index was 48339 (12019 - 201026). Views, upload day, and video duration were significantly higher for High Quality group ($p = 0.001$, $p = 0.004$, and $p < 0.001$, respectively). Likes and dislikes were not significantly different between groups. The popularity score was significantly higher for Low Quality group (37 (IQR: 6 - 119), $p = 0.023$), while the power index was significantly higher for High Quality group (72066 (IQR: 9879 - 217004), $p = 0.002$).

Conclusions: Although some high-quality videos on gestational hypertension are available on YouTube, the overall reliability, accuracy, and comprehensiveness remain limited. Notably, higher quality information is not associated with higher levels of popularity. It is important for healthcare providers to direct patients to reliable sources and promote awareness on how to discern the quality of online health information.

PEER REVIEW STATEMENT

This paper has undergone a double-blind peer review process and has been approved by the scientific committee of the conference.

KEYWORDS

YouTube, hypertension, gestational hypertension, social network, pregnancy.

CONFLICT OF INTEREST DECLARATION

There is no commercial, financial, or personal conflict of interest in this study.

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